

A NOTE ON THE ETHYLATION *p*-NITROPHENOL

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p-Nitrophenetole constitutes the starting material for the manufacture of phenacetin, an important synthetic drug. Nitrophenetole is generally prepared by heating the sodium salt of *p*-nitrophenol with ethyl chloride in an autoclave or with ethyl bromide at ordinary pressure.

The present investigation has been undertaken to see if the ethylation of *p*-nitrophenol can be successfully carried out by using ethyl hydrogen sulphate or ethyl potassium sulphate, both of which are cheaper than ethyl chloride or ethyl bromide. It has been found that ethyl hydrogen sulphate has very little action on *p*-nitrophenol and by using it, a very negligible yield of *p*-nitrophenetole is obtained (*vide* Experimental).

However, the use of ethyl potassium sulphate for ethylation on *p*-nitrophenol appears to be much more promising and under certain conditions *p*-nitrophenetole has been obtained in 71.5% yield. The results obtained are recorded in Table I.

T A B L E I

20 G. of the sodium salt of *p*-nitrophenol and 100 c.c. water were used in each experiment.

Expt. No.	Ethyl potassium sulphate.	Experimental condition.	Period of heating.	Yield of uncrystallised <i>p</i> -nitrophenetole	
				in gm.	percentage of theory
1	50 g.	Refluxing on wire-gauze	20 hrs.	2.6 g.	12.5
2	"	"	36	9	43.6
3	80	"	20	7.4	35.7
4	"	"	36	11.8	57
5	80	110—120° (autoclave)	7	6	29
6	"	125—130° (autoclave)	7	9	43.6
7	80	" "	7	12	58
8	"	" "	16	14.8	71.5
9	"	" "	24	14.8	71.5

It is significant to note in this connection that when a mixture of equimolecular proportions of *p*-nitrophenetole and sodium-potassium sulphate in 20% alcohol is heated in an autoclave at 125-130° for 10 hours, no trace of *p*-nitrophenol is obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Action of Ethyl hydrogen Sulphate on p-Nitrophenol

(a) *p*-Nitrophenol (20 g.) was added to a mixture of absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3.5 c.c.), and the mixture was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 10 hours. Alcohol was then distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated solid, after filtration, was triturated with excess of 5% aqueous caustic soda solution, filtered and washed thoroughly with water. A residue (0.4 g., 1.7% of theory) was left, which on crystallisation from alcohol, was proved to be *p*-nitrophenetole by mixed m.p. (58-60°), with a genuine sample.

(b) When the above reaction was carried out in a closed vessel at 80° for 10 hours, the yield of (uncrystallised) *p*-nitrophenetole came up to 1 g. (4.2% of theory).

(c) There was no formation of *p*-nitrophenetole when a mixture of ethyl hydrogen-sulphate (prepared as above, by mixing absolute alcohol with concentrated sulphuric acid in equimolecular proportions) and the sodium salt of *p*-nitrophenol was heated in presence of absolute alcohol on the water-bath for 10-12 hours.

(d) Ethyl hydrogen sulphate was prepared by treating ethyl potassium sulphate (112 g., prepared according to the method recorded in *Bull. soc. chim.*, 19, 295), suspended in alcohol (200 c.c.), with concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.8, 37.2 c.c.) under cooling. The mixture was filtered and the clear filtrate, mixed with *p*-nitrophenol (20 g.), was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 10 hours. Alcohol was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with an excess of 5% aqueous caustic soda solution filtered and thoroughly washed with water. The residue (1.4 g., 5.8% of theory) was crystallised and proved to be *p*-nitrophenetole.

When the above reaction was carried out in an autoclave at 80° for 10 hours, the yield of (uncrystallised) *p*-nitrophenetole came up to 25 g. (10.4% of theory).

Action of Ethyl potassium sulphate on the sodium salt of p-Nitrophenol
—To a mixture of ethyl potassium sulphate (80 g.) and water (100 c.c.) was added the sodium salt of *p*-nitrophenol (20 g.). The resulting mixture was then heated in an autoclave at 125-130° for 16 hours. Subsequently the mixture was treated with an excess of 5% aqueous caustic soda solution and filtered. The residue was thoroughly washed with water and dried; yield 14.8 g. (71.5% of theory). It was proved to be *p*-nitrophenetole.

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